

Research On The Development Of Undergraduate Vocational Education -- Taking Guizhou Vocational Education As An Example

Li Yanyan, Zhang Jiayong

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 01 , 2022</p> <p>Accepted: February 02, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : undergraduate Vocational Education,Guizhou</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7600151</p>	<p><i>Since the founding of the People's Republic of China, China's vocational education has developed vigorously and has been expanding in scale. By 2021, there are 29,148,400 students in vocational education, including 13,118,100 in secondary vocational schools and 16,030,300 in higher vocational colleges. Such a huge scale has effectively supported the economic, social and industrial development. And with the scale expansion, we also found problems. At present, the number of students in undergraduate vocational education in China is only 129,300, accounting for 0.81% of the existing students in higher vocational colleges. As a new product of social development and vocational education development, undergraduate-level vocational education still has a long way to go in the future.</i></p>

Introduction

For a long time, vocational education has been staying at the specialized level and become the level education in general education. Compared with undergraduate education, it has become "secondary education", "broken education" and "end education". How to change the embarrassing situation of vocational education has become an urgent problem. In June 2014, the State Council issued "about the decision to speed up the development of modern vocational education", in the decision: " in the future China will explore the development of undergraduate level of higher vocational education, build technical secondary school, specialized, this, the integration of modern vocational education system, receive undergraduate level vocational education students to reach a certain scale, actively develop graduate level of higher vocational education."The 2019 National Vocational Education Reform Implementation Plan (hereinafter referred to as vocational Education 20) clearly requires:" By 2022, the teaching conditions of vocational colleges will basically meet the standards, a large number of ordinary undergraduate institutions of higher learning will be transformed into application-oriented applications, and 50 high-level higher vocational schools and 150 backbone majors (groups) will be built. China has established a standard system for vocational education covering most industries and fields and with internationally advanced standards. We will carry out trials of vocational education at the undergraduate level."The first batch of 15 vocational and technical universities were formally established in that year. By August 2021, a total of 32 vocational and technical universities had been established nationwide (Figure 1). On May 1,2022, the Vocational Education Law of the People's Republic of China was officially implemented after 25 years later. Article 15 stipulates: " The education of higher vocational schools shall be carried out by higher vocational schools of junior college, undergraduate and above education level and ordinary institutions of higher learning."Solved the problem of undergraduate level vocational education at the legal level.

职业本科分布情况

(Figure 1) Distribution map of vocational and technical universities

In 2020, the Ministry of Education and nine other departments issued the Action Plan for Improving the Quality and Training of Vocational Education (2020-2023), proposing: "The development of undergraduate vocational education should be regarded as a key link in improving the modern vocational education system, cultivate high-quality innovative technical and technical talents, and smooth the growth channels of technical and technical talents. We will steadily promote trials of vocational education at the undergraduate level, and support qualified units of high-level higher vocational schools with Chinese characteristics in pilot vocational education. We will promote the transformation of qualified ordinary undergraduate universities into application-oriented universities. According to the needs of the industry and the characteristics of the industry, the government will appropriately expand the scale of professional master's and doctoral degrees, and promote the development of professional graduate students oriented by professional needs, focusing on practical ability training, and taking the combination of industry, university, research and application." This means that the highest level of vocational education, the same as general education, will reach a doctorate. At the same time, the multi-path creation of vocational undergraduate education will become a development trend. On January 22, 2021, the general office of the Ministry of Education issued the undergraduate level vocational education professional setting management method (trial) "(faculty into hall [2021, no. 1) notice," college set undergraduate level vocational education should be closely around the national and regional economic and social industry development in key areas, service industry new forms, new mode, docking new career, focusing on long schooling training related professional. This fully reflects the important role of vocational education, especially undergraduate vocational education, in the national economy and regional industrial development." In the undergraduate level of vocational education supporting management system has been introduced.

In April 2021, the National Vocational Education Conference was held in Beijing. General Secretary Xi Jinping has made important instructions, stressing: "We should build a number of high-level vocational colleges and majors, promote the integration of vocational education, enhance the adaptability of vocational education, accelerate the construction of a modern vocational education system, and train more high-quality technical personnel, skilled craftsmen and craftsmen of a major country." Premier Li Keqiang issued a statement: "We should strengthen the construction of teachers and school conditions in vocational schools, optimize and improve teaching materials and teaching methods, explore the apprenticeship system with Chinese characteristics, pay attention to the cultivation of students' craftsman spirit and the habit of excellence, and strive to cultivate hundreds of millions of high-quality technical and skilled personnel." The important instructions and instructions of the General Secretary and the Premier have become an important opportunity for the development of vocational education. The undergraduate level vocational education, as a high-level construction direction of vocational colleges, has become the goal of many colleges and universities. In October 2021, the General Offices of the CPC Central Committee and the State Council issued the Opinions on Promoting the High-quality Development of Modern Vocational Education, stressing that "By 2025, vocational education

types will be more distinctive, the modern vocational education system will be basically completed, and the construction of a skilled society will be promoted in an all-round way. The pattern of running schools has been further optimized, and the conditions for running schools have been greatly improved. The enrollment scale of vocational undergraduate education should be no less than 10% of that of higher vocational education, and the attractiveness and quality of vocational education have been significantly improved. By 2035, the overall level of vocational education will be among the top in the world, and a skilled society will be basically completed. The social status of technical and skilled personnel has been greatly improved, the supply of vocational education has been highly in line with the demand for economic and social development, and their role in comprehensively building a modern socialist country has been significantly enhanced."Encourage application-oriented undergraduate schools to carry out vocational undergraduate education level through. Gradually realize the mutual selection and credit recognition of courses at all stages of vocational education.

The emergence to the development of vocational education at the undergraduate level fully reflects the demands of social development, economic construction, industrial urgent need and the people. It is the inevitable result of the joint action of external demand and internal demand, and the promotion of vocational education as a type of education in the educational structure. At present, undergraduate level vocational education is in its initial stage, which will also cause some specific problems. Whether in the development or in the satisfaction of the demands of all parties, there will be some disputes and the adjustment and improvement in the operation. Undergraduate-level vocational education should carry out in-depth research while gaining attention. This study will conduct an in-depth analysis of "developing undergraduate level vocational education" to solve the consensus and cognitive problems. At the same time, it focuses on solving the core problem of "how to develop undergraduate level vocational education". The research will try to establish a theoretical infrastructure on the basic, frontier and development expectations of vocational education at the undergraduate level, which can provide some valuable references for policy makers and practical implementers.

.2 1 The status quo of the study

In this study, China CNKI (CNKI) digital library was set as the source database of data, subject search was set as the search condition, "undergraduate level vocational education" and "technical undergraduate" were set as the key search terms, the search time was set from January 1996 to January 2022, and a total of 799 documents were obtained. Through reading and analysis one by one, 181 irrelevant newspapers and comments were deleted, and finally 618 valid texts were obtained, and exported in Refworks format. On the analysis of the literature, Citespace software was used to visualize the obtained samples, using the version 5.7.R3.SE.

After sorting out the literature, the time of the paper was published in detail (Figure 2). From the trend of literature research, before 2010, there were few studies on vocational education at the undergraduate level, and the research topics were very scattered and there was no systematic formation. Most of them are talking about the importance and necessity of developing vocational education at the undergraduate level, and some individual researchers have put forward some construction ideas for learning from foreign development experience. In 2014, the Decision of The State Council on Accelerating the Development of Modern Vocational Education promulgated by the state has become a watershed for research. During this period, the study of undergraduate level vocational education has discussed the feasibility and development based on the theoretical level. With the introduction of relevant policies on the establishment and development of vocational education at the undergraduate level, the research trend from 2015 to 2017 began to fall. The main reason for the fall is that the policy has been introduced, and the original forecast has lost its significance. After 2019, with the gradual clear guidance of various policies, the operation mode of vocational education at the undergraduate level has gradually become clear, and the pilot work has been actually carried out. According to the practical problems and solutions encountered, the research on vocational education at the undergraduate level has increased again. However, there is still a directional trend of research policy and policy interpretation in the research, and there is no systematic and independent thinking, which also leads to the focus of the research direction.

(Figure 2) Analysis of the literature volume change of vocational education at the undergraduate level

1.2.1 Analysis of the literature

Literature publishers refer to the retrieved literature authors, who have more in-depth research in this research field. According to the statistical results of the literature, we found that there are 685 authors in the field of undergraduate vocational education research (statistics to the third author). According to Derek John de Solla Price's theory, $N=0.749 N_{max}$, the authors of N or more papers published in this field are the core literature authors of this study. The collected author data was substituted into $0.749 / 134$ (the total number of papers published by scholars with the largest number of papers in this field is 13, as shown in Figure 3). Therefore, we concluded that the number of papers published in the field of undergraduate vocational education, greater than or equal to 4, are the core authors of the current research in this field. Statistics yielded 114 core authors, accounting for 16.64% of the total number of authors. The number of articles by the 114 authors was 234, accounting for 37.86% of the total. The network density analysis of cooperation among authors through Citespace yielded a density of 0.0014, indicating that there is almost little research cooperation between authors, which, to some extent, also limits the problem about the depth of research in vocational education research at the undergraduate level.

2.2.1 Analysis based on literature research keywords

The key words extracted in the whole article are not only the subject of the research, but also the center of the research. The 618 valid samples retrieved in this time were analyzed by Citespace software, with time partition selection from 1996 to 2022, time interval selection set to "1", node type selection "keyword", "top30", and algorithm selection "Putting sliced networks" and "Minimum Spanning Tree". 447 nodes and 943 connections were obtained to generate the co-occurrence map of keywords (as shown in Figure 3). The larger the nodes are, the higher the frequency and frequency of the keywords are.

By analyzing the keywords, word frequency and mediation degree, the nodes with mediation degree greater than 0.1 indicate that they are in an important position in the research. In this sample, the nodes with intermediary degree greater than 0.1 are higher vocational education (0.39), undergraduate level (0.35), vocational education (0.21), vocational education (0.19), undergraduate level vocational education (0.16), and modern vocational education system (0.10) (see Table 1 for details). It can be found that these keywords have become a hot issue of scholars' attention and research in recent years. The internal and external perspectives of undergraduate vocational education research are analyzed respectively.

序号	关键词	词频/次	中介度	序号	关键词	词频/次	中介度
1	高等职业教育	89	0.39	21	必要性	11	0.02
2	职业教育	83	0.21	22	技术本科	10	0.02
3	本科层次	81	0.35	23	现代职教体系	10	0.01
4	本科层次职业教育	70	0.16	24	职业本科	10	0.02
5	高职教育	47	0.19	25	技术本科教育	10	0.02
6	现代职业教育体系	35	0.1	26	层次结构	9	0.03
7	高职本科	29	0.08	27	转型发展	9	0.01
8	应用型本科	29	0.06	28	培养模式	9	0.01
9	人才培养	28	0.07	29	技术教育	9	0.02
10	人才培养模式	25	0.05	30	地方本科院校	9	0.01
11	高职院校	24	0.05	31	教育类型	8	0.03
12	本科	23	0.07	32	衔接	8	0.01
13	应用技术大学	20	0.05	33	人才培养方案	7	0.02
14	本科职业教育	19	0.05	34	现代职业教育	7	0.02
15	转型	14	0.01	35	人才培养目标	7	0.02
16	校企合作	13	0.03	36	培养体系	6	0.02
17	定位	13	0.03	37	应用型人才	6	0.03
18	高职	13	0.01	38	新建本科院校	6	0.01
19	职业教育体系	11	0.01	39	高等教育	6	0.01
20	本科教育	11	0.01	40	创新发展	6	0

Table 1 Frequency and mediation degree analysis table of literature keywords

From the perspective of internal research in vocational education at the undergraduate level, the talent training mode and talent training goal are the research fields that scholars pay the most attention to. Song Kehui believes that the society needs not only the research talents who discover and study the objective laws, but also the applied talents who use the objective laws and scientific principles to transform the world and create direct benefits for the human society. These two types of talents should have different emphasis on the training specifications. Compared with the research-oriented talents who understand the world, applied talents belong to the type of talents who transform the world. They undertake the important task of transforming academic research results into social production practice and creating material or non-material forms with practical value for human society. Therefore, according to the transformation process of academic research results, application talents are divided into three categories: engineering application talents, skilled application talents and technical application talents according to their vocational types. Tu to hui put forward undergraduate level of higher vocational education talent training target should be "training with strong technical theoretical basis, practical skills and application ability, and serve the production, construction and management of the first line of advanced technical applied talents, namely training technical engineers or field engineer", clear talent training should have "emphasis on technology, outstanding application, pay attention to skills, pay attention to innovation, both humanities" connotation, this is the premise and condition of building talent training mode.

From the perspective of external research of undergraduate vocational education, the necessity of developing undergraduate vocational education is a hot issue. Shi Weiping, Xu Guoqing in the trial on the significance of Chinese development technology and strategy, points out the development of undergraduate level vocational technology education training technology applied talents in the necessity under the background of economic and social development, and from the needs of the technology development, the needs of the humanized education, for the international trend of education object three aspects discusses the development of undergraduate level vocational technology education important strategic significance. Li Xiaoming pointed out that the gap of a large number of senior applied technical talents has become the main "bottleneck" restricting the adjustment of industrial structure and the upgrading of technical structure. In order to meet this demand, it is an inevitable trend for China's higher vocational education to extend to a higher level, and it is imperative to develop vocational education at the undergraduate level. Xiao Haitao and Xiang Chun put forward: with the continuous improvement of technical level, the continuous generation and increase of high-tech positions, the requirements for post ability are also constantly improved, the vocational education at the specialized level can no longer meet the needs, the undergraduate level vocational education should be developed.

1.2.3 Research and comment on undergraduate-level vocational education

(1) Research on the necessity of developing vocational education at the undergraduate level

1. It is helpful to the complete system framework of vocational education as a type of education. A perfect vocational education system needs its effective connection and connection between the internal elements. Song

Lianxi put forward that the vocational education undergraduate course has a unique value in the vocational education system. Only the undergraduate vocational education and the professional master's education exist in the vocational education system, and the modern vocational education system is complete. Lu Suju proposed that the trial of undergraduate vocational education will open up the channel for students to rise and make the path of upward development more accessible. Xu Han put forward that the development of technical education at the undergraduate level will certainly enhance the cohesion and attraction of vocational education, and contribute to the improvement of the vocational education system. Ma Shuchao et al. proposed that in recent years, the country has actively explored the establishment of a professional degree system, connected it with the professional master's degree, and promoted the construction of a modern vocational education system at the institutional level.

2. It helps to meet the needs of senior technical talents in economic development and technological innovation. From a domestic perspective, China has put forward the strategic plan of "Made in China 2025", new infrastructure and other national action programs. It aims to comprehensively improve the competitiveness of the manufacturing industry. The comprehensive improvement of the manufacturing industry requires a large number of high-level innovative technical and technical talents. Shi Weiping, Ma Yan and other experts put forward that the original senior technical talents who only pass through the natural growth mode cannot meet the requirements of economic development, and the gap of senior application-oriented technical talents provides a broad space for the development of undergraduate vocational education in China. Zhou Jianglin proposed that technical undergraduate courses can meet the needs of high-level technical talents for building an innovative national strategy. Liu Xiaotian et al. put forward that from the international perspective, according to the background of undergraduate vocational education in Germany, Japan, Britain and Taiwan, China, the emergence and development of undergraduate vocational education is an inevitable requirement for the evolution of industrial structure from labor-intensive industry to capital and technology-intensive industry. Yan Xueyi puts forward that: in order to meet the needs of technological innovation, the speed of technical undergraduate development in developed countries is much higher than that of technical specialty, which is the common development trend of technical education in developed countries and regions in recent years. No matter from the perspective of domestic economic and technological development needs or from the perspective of international experience reference and the development trend in recent years, the development of undergraduate level vocational education is helpful to meet the needs of economic development and technological innovation for senior technical talents.

3. It helps to meet the needs of individuals receiving vocational education to receive higher levels of education. The level and space of upward mobility of higher vocational students are limited, and the proportion of "upgrading only" in higher vocational students is relatively low. Graduation of junior college education level has become the "end" of most people who choose vocational education types. In recent years, as some private undergraduate colleges and universities have been included in the work of the "upgrading", the enrollment of "upgrading" students has been effectively expanded. In February 2022, the Ministry of Education press conference, the proportion of college students entering junior college has reached 20%. However, students only have one opportunity to take the exam in the graduation year, and the increase of employment pressure also increases the number of applicants year by year. Both students' demands for college admission and the needs of economic and social development are far from being met. Zhang Heng put forward: the vocational education limited to the junior college level causes students, parents do not recognize the higher vocational education, to solve the higher vocational "junior college" level of the identity problem is urgent. Chen Baohua proposed that the vocational education at the specialized level can not meet the needs of people to receive a higher level of education. Nie Wei pointed out that many high-quality students of vocational education have flowed to Taiwan or abroad to receive a higher level of vocational education, to seek greater space for development. If they are provided with a higher platform to study, it will not only reduce the number of educational resources and brain drain, but also improve the attractiveness of vocational education. Fan Mingcheng put forward that higher vocational education should expand at the level to the undergraduate and graduate level, and realize the diversification of higher vocational education levels, which not only reflects the requirements of the law of external relations of education, but also better meets the individual enrollment needs, which has become the trend of the development of higher vocational education in the world. The development of vocational education at the undergraduate level and the construction of a modern vocational education system from secondary vocational education to professional doctors can help to meet the needs of individuals receiving vocational education to receive higher levels of education. In summary, the research of Chinese scholars on the necessity of undergraduate vocational education is rich and comprehensive. Future research can start from the advantages of vocational education and the development of vocational education at the undergraduate level. For example, the development of undergraduate vocational education is beneficial to enhance the attractiveness of vocational education; obtaining undergraduate degree after graduation will make some students choose vocational education when applying in the college entrance examination. At the same time, it can also be analyzed from the perspective of the relationship between vocational education and general education. Is the development of

undergraduate-level vocational education conducive to the equality of vocational education and general education? Therefore, different research perspectives on the necessity of developing vocational education at the undergraduate level are still under further analysis and exploration.

(2) Research on organizing the subject of vocational education at the undergraduate level

1. Private higher vocational colleges are upgraded to undergraduate level vocational colleges. Hainan Vocational University of Science and Technology, Guangxi City Vocational University belong to this category. In the development of private vocational education, it does not rely on the state appropriation, and develops vigorously under the support of the Law of the Promotion of Private Education of the People's Republic of China and its Implementation Regulations. With the change of national policies, private higher vocational colleges are no longer upgraded to ordinary undergraduate courses, and have gradually become the main force of undergraduate level vocational education. Guo Ran put forward: "The promotion of the development of private vocational education is inseparable from the promotion of the teaching level, and the vocational education at the undergraduate level is a way of development."

2. Public higher vocational colleges will merge and establish undergraduate vocational education with the help of independent colleges. Lanzhou Vocational And Technical University of Resources and Environment and Guiyang Kangyang Vocational University belong to this category. With the help of the educational qualifications, teachers, teaching facilities and professional construction of the existing independent colleges, it will be merged into vocational education at the undergraduate level. Give full play to their respective advantages and strengths in the union, and improve the level of teaching while maintaining the essence of vocational education. Although the form is good, but in the actual operation has encountered no small resistance. In June 2021, Hunan, Jiangxi and other provinces issued intensive instructions on the transfer of independent colleges to vocational education at the undergraduate level. "Old methods for the old and new methods for the new people" were implemented in various places, which slowed down the pace of merger and transfer to some extent.

3. Application-oriented undergraduate universities to apply for vocational undergraduate majors. Relying on the existing undergraduate level education resources, we will open professional undergraduate majors. In May 2022, the General Office of the Ministry of Education announced the Notice on announcing the Filing Results of Vocational Undergraduate Education in 2022, among which 160 majors from 15 applied undergraduate universities were successfully filed. Formed the first batch of local application-oriented undergraduate universities to provide undergraduate level vocational education. Xu Hui put forward: from the perspective of talent training, the talent training specifications of some ordinary undergraduate colleges and universities in China, especially engineering colleges and universities, belong to technical application-oriented talents, and the training objectives of schools are basically consistent with the training objectives of higher vocational education.

4. Some high-quality public higher vocational colleges have been independently upgraded to undergraduate level vocational education. At present, only Nanjing Polytechnic Vocational and Technical University is upgraded in this form. As the first vocational named school in Chinese history, it has been established for more than a hundred years. The university has become one of the first batch of pilot institutions for undergraduate level vocational education by the Ministry of Education by virtue of its own advantages. Shi Weiping, Xu Guoqing and others proposed that higher vocational colleges have some experience in technical education, internal technical learning equipment, "double-qualified" teachers, clear talent training plan, and rich resources and industry background outside. Gu Guangfu and Zou Jiquan put forward that some of the selected higher vocational colleges have the ability and conditions to hold vocational education in some characteristic brand majors, so the higher vocational colleges with superior conditions can be upgraded to undergraduate vocational colleges through strict examination. The existing high-quality vocational college is one of the main bodies of undergraduate level vocational education.

Based on the past scholars' research on the development path of vocational education at the undergraduate level, the scholars have different perspectives and positions, so analyzed by relying on higher education or vocational education. The research of scholars is mainly based on the research of the development path of undergraduate and higher vocational colleges at the macro level, and explains the path at the theoretical level, without analyzing and demonstrating whether the path is feasible from the perspective of practice. As the country in 2019,2020 undergraduate level vocational education officially on the historical stage, in the future research, believe that there will be more researchers adopt the method of empirical research, has opened the undergraduate level vocational education situation and quality tracking research, analysis of the problems existing in the operation, for the next stage of the development of undergraduate level vocational education to provide more reference.

(3) Research on the training objectives of vocational education at the undergraduate level

Vocational education at the undergraduate level has the dual attributes of vocational education and undergraduate education at the level of type, so the talent training of vocational education at the undergraduate level should not only meet the requirements of vocational education focusing on technical skills, but also meet the requirements of multi-application scenarios of undergraduate education. Xia Jianguo put forward that the

training objectives of undergraduate vocational education should be "senior technical talents", "technical talents", "innovative, compound, industrial and high-level talents with the ability of sustainable development". Although scholars have differences in the wording of training objectives, they believe that vocational education at the undergraduate level should cultivate high-level compound talents with profound and solid theoretical foundation, superb practical ability and novel and unique creative thinking. With the acceleration of industrial transformation and upgrading, scholars have concluded in recent years that the sustainable development of learning ability is also one of the indispensable abilities of undergraduate vocational education talents.

A comprehensive analysis of the research results in recent years shows that the research only explains from a macro perspective that we should cultivate both theoretical and technical ability professionals. What is the difference between them and general undergraduate education? In 2020 issued by the Ministry of Education of the well of the 2021 session of the national ordinary college graduates employment entrepreneurship work notice requirements: "to promote the party and government organs, institutions, state-owned enterprises take the lead to reverse only school degree of choose and employ persons, in the recruitment announcement and practice shall not graduate from colleges, countries (border) outside the learning experience, learning style (full-time and part-time) as a restrictive condition." This means that ordinary undergraduate, professional undergraduate or even part-time undergraduate stand on the same starting line. It is imperative to give full play to its own advantages, highlight the characteristics of vocational education and study the development of undergraduate vocational education.

(4) Research on the setting up of vocational education majors at the undergraduate level

As for the professional setting of undergraduate vocational education, some scholars conclude from the theoretical perspective that the major of undergraduate vocational education should be set up according to the needs of local development. Liang Yanqing, Yang Zhaohui and so on pointed out that the professional setting of higher vocational undergraduate colleges should serve the regional development, and take the first line of economic construction and the first line of production, service and management as the entry point of professional setting, so as to cultivate technical application-oriented talents for the local economy. Yang Xiaoyan pointed out that only when undergraduate vocational education serves the local economic development can it have the space for its survival and development. Other scholars take specific schools as an example to analyze how to build vocational education majors at the undergraduate level according to the characteristics of different majors. Chu Qiang and Li Sen pointed out that, taking Shanghai Public Security University as an example, efforts should be made to strengthen the professional construction and talent training of talents in short supply, such as economic investigation, criminal science, network security, police command and tactics, and anti-terrorism. How should the professional setting of undergraduate course level vocational education be positioned? Is to follow the secondary vocational and higher vocational training mode, or improve knowledge and ability. In the existing examination, most of the implementation of the "university by major enrollment plan", and the original major or related majors to undergraduate colleges and universities, to a certain extent limited the training needs of compound talents. Facing the secondary "composite" of knowledge and skills. Therefore, in the professional setting, it should not only be able to attract students to apply for the examination, but also help students to find a job suitable for their major and ability in the job market after graduation. How should the major of undergraduate vocational education level set? It needs further research to realize the characteristics of highlighting the level of undergraduate education and the consideration of the same nature of vocational education.

(5) Research on the curriculum system of undergraduate-level vocational education

The past scholars' research on the curriculum system of undergraduate level vocational education mainly starts from two aspects. Based on the problems existing in the curriculum system of vocational education at the undergraduate level in China, some scholars show that there are some problems in the curriculum system of undergraduate level vocational education in China, such as weak employment leading function and not specific curriculum standards. Based on the above actual situation, China should adhere to the type of vocational education in terms of curriculum concept, and build a curriculum model of connecting the professional skills and posts of undergraduate vocational education. Jiang Xianqun et al. pointed out that the curriculum mode connected with the post has the characteristics of clear curriculum standards, curriculum content breaking through the constraints of discipline structure, project and task as the main form, deep cooperation in curriculum management, and complete curriculum functions. The other scholars study the characteristics of undergraduate vocational education curriculum system in Germany, Japan, Taiwan, China and other developed countries and regions and summarize its characteristics to provide reference for the setting of undergraduate vocational education courses in China. For example, through the study of the curriculum system of undergraduate vocational education in Taiwan, some scholars put forward that the characteristics of its curriculum setting include: diversified curriculum theme development, curriculum implementation focuses on the advanced cultivation of students' ability, and flexible and diversified curriculum setting. By studying the undergraduate curriculum system of vocational education in Berlin University of Technology and Economics, scholars believe that China's undergraduate vocational education curriculum system should set up ability-oriented modular

curriculum, change the traditional curriculum teaching method and introduce general curriculum certification standards to implement evaluation.

(6) Research on the teaching staff of vocational education at the undergraduate level

The abilities that undergraduate level vocational education teachers should have should be diversified. In terms of knowledge, teachers should have professional knowledge, teachers' professional knowledge and innovative guidance knowledge. In terms of skills, the "double teacher" qualifications, technical ability, operational ability, practical ability and enterprise experience of vocational school teachers are equally important. Jia Junli, Tang Zhenhua and others should have the ability of practice, teaching and innovation; establish scientific view of talent and educating people; in social service level, undergraduate teachers of vocational colleges should strengthen cooperative communication and achievement transformation. Based on the research and analysis of existing scholars, vocational education teachers at the undergraduate level should not only consolidate their professional theoretical knowledge, but also improve their practical skills. In terms of ideology and social services, they should also keep up with the requirements of The Times for vocational education teachers and constantly improve their ideological height. Overall, the undergraduate level of vocational education teachers quality requirements more comprehensive, practical, in the national vocational education reform implementation plan: " vocational colleges, applied undergraduate university related professional teachers in principle from more than 3 years working experience and with higher vocational education above personnel open recruitment, special skilled talents (including senior above professional qualification personnel) can be appropriate degree requirements, since 2020 basic recruitment from fresh graduates."It can be seen that the requirements of vocational education for teachers are also changing, from only education to the enterprise experience in professional skills. In the subsequent research, how to realize the quantitative standard of teacher training, source, experience and skills can become an important direction of research.

(7) Factors hindering the development of vocational education at the undergraduate level

1. The society has insufficient understanding of vocational education at the undergraduate level, and has held contempt and prejudice for vocational education for a long time. In real life, many people equate technical workers with migrant workers, forming the cognition that vocational education is equal to migrant workers. In reality, the gap between the treatment and status of practitioners is the main factor that causes the difficulties in the development of vocational education. Hu Jianyong and Zhang Ying pointed out that ordinary colleges and universities are also influenced by the inertia of traditional academic education. When choosing the school orientation, they aim at "academic" and "research", and do not want to choose "vocational education" to reduce their identity. The above scholars believe that it is because vocational education itself is in a despised position, which leads to problems in the promotion of undergraduate vocational education derived from the specialized level. Other scholars believe that people believe that high-level technical personnel can be trained by science education or engineering education, and that technical undergraduate education is not necessary to exist independently. Xu Han pointed out that in the higher education system, even if people are unconsciously engaged in technology education, they are not willing to position themselves in technology education. The above scholars believe that it is the fuzzy positioning of undergraduate vocational education itself that makes people have wrong ideas, which has also become an important reason for restricting its development.

2. The quality and ability of teachers cannot meet the talent training needs of vocational education at the undergraduate level. Through the analysis of the subjects of undergraduate vocational colleges, it is found that the main types of undergraduate vocational schools in China are independent college transformation, the upgrading of vocational colleges and the upgrading of independent vocational colleges. Among these three types of school teachers, most of the teachers in independent colleges lack practical ability, especially practical ability, while most of the teachers in vocational colleges lack scientific research ability. Lian Xiaoqing and Kong Deying pointed out that in terms of teachers' personal ability, scholars generally believe that teachers at the undergraduate level have contradictions such as incomplete high technology knowledge and the separation of professional ability and normal ability. Ling Qifan put forward that in vocational colleges, teachers have problems in undergraduate vocational education in the structure of supply and demand of teachers, the orientation of teacher talent training and relevant standards. The above problems will lead to a series of problems, such as the weakening of professional service ability, the deviation of the direction of talent training, and the difficulty of systematic and scientific teacher education courses, which cannot quickly escape from the original education and teaching track, and then change the content, which has an impact on the subsequent development.

Reference

Chinese works:

- [1] By Li Jiayang (2020). *Comparative study on the development of vocational education in the 70 years of New China*. Kunming: Yunnan University Press.
- [2] Huo Shaozhou (1988). *system theory*. Beijing: Science and Technology Academic Press.

- [3] Huang Dandan, et al. (2012). *The future of higher vocational education*. Beijing: The Commercial Press.
- [4] [Ancient Rome] Cicero, Cicero (2006). *Three theories: on friendship, on the old age, on responsibility*. Beijing: Unity Publishing House.
- [5] Hu Lin (2020). *Craftsman spirit and vocational education*. Shenyang: Liaohai Publishing House.
- [6] Education Dictionary Compilation Committee (1991). *The Great Dictionary of Education (Volume 3)*. Shanghai: Shanghai Education Press.
- [7] By the China Development Research Foundation (2021). *The road of vocational education development*. Beijing: China Development Press.
- [8] Huang Yao (2009). *Vocational pedagogy — principle and application*. Beijing: Higher Education Press.
- [9] Xia Jinxing (2013). *Practical topics of vocational education*. Beijing: Beijing Normal University Press.
- [10] Yang Hanqing, Han Jia (2003). *An Introduction to Comparative Higher Education*. Beijing: The People's Education Press.
- [11] Xu Liangying, Zhao Zhongli, and Zhang Xuan (1979). *The Albert Einstein Collection, Volume III*. Beijing: The Commercial Press.
- [12] Li Min, Li Xingrong (2021). *An Introduction to the Regulations of Higher Vocational Education*. Chengdu: Southwestern University of Finance and Economics Press.
- [13] Compilation group of New Ideas, New Views and New Measures (2012). *New ideas, new ideas and new initiatives*. Beijing: Hongqi Publishing House.
- [14] Xiao Hua shift (2006). *Review the quality and standards of higher vocational education*. Shanghai: Published by East China Normal University organized body.
- [15] Translation by Li Kang.(Original book) (2003). *The evolution of educational thought*. Shanghai: Shanghai People's Publishing House.
- [16] Translation by Zou Jin (original Carl Jaspers) (1991). *What is education*. Shanghai: Sanlian Bookstore.
- [17] Zhang Jing (2011). *Enterprise University Studies*. Beijing: Economic Science Press,
- [18] Translated by Wang Chengxu (the original book by Burton Clark) (2003). *Establishing an entrepreneurial university: a way of organizational transformation*. Beijing: The People's Education Press.
- [19] *The Complete Works of Marx and Engels (Vol. 2)* (1957). Beijing: People's Publishing House.
- [20] *The Complete Works of Marx and Engels (Vol. 1)* (1956). Beijing: People's Publishing House.
- [21] Gu Yong'an (2012). *Theory on transformation and development of new undergraduate colleges*. Beijing: China Social Sciences Press.
- [22] Huang Yao (2011). *A Study on the sustainable Development Strategy of vocational education*. Beijing: Higher Education Press.
- [23] He Guoqing, Wang Baoxing, et al. (2003). *The History of Foreign Higher Education*. Beijing: The People's Education Press.
- [24] Huang Futao (2003). *The History of Foreign Higher Education*. Shanghai: Shanghai Education Press.
- [25] Teng Dachun (2005). *The General History of Foreign Education (Vol. 6)*. Jinan: Shandong Education Press.
- [26] Ma Luting (2006). *College structure in the promotion of science and technology*. Guangzhou: Guangdong Higher Education Press.
- [27] Liu Chunsheng, Xu Changfa (2002). *Vocational pedagogy*. Beijing: Educational Science Press.
- [28] UNESCO (2004). *Education- -the wealth lies in it*. Beijing: Educational Science Press.
- [29] Li Quansheng (2005). *Educational economics and management*. Tianjin: Tianjin People's Publishing House.
- [30] Zhou Xiaomu, translated by Han Hui (the original work of John Holland) (2000). *Hidden order — Adaptation creates complexity*. Shanghai: Shanghai Science and Technology Education Press.
- [31] Wu Qingji (1998). *Transformation and development of technical and vocational education — the practice of enhancing national competitiveness*. Taipei: issued by Normal University.
- [32] *Selected Works of Marx and Engels (Vol. 4)* (1975). Beijing: People's Publishing House.
- [33] Lv Da, Zhou Msheng (2004). *Famous literature of contemporary Foreign education reform (British Volume 1)*. Beijing: The People's Education Press.
- [34] Wang Jing, Zhao Suisheng (original Charles Hemel) (1983). *Education of today is for the world of tomorrow*. Beijing: China Foreign Translation and Publishing Company.
- [35] Wang Chengxu, et al. (Frans F. Van Fuert) (2001). *A Comparative Study on the International Higher Education Policy*. Hangzhou: Zhejiang Education Press.
- [36] Jiang Dayuan (2013). *Research on the development trend of contemporary world vocational education*. Beijing: Press of Electronic Electronics Industry.
- [37] Yuan Zhenguo (1995). *Confrontation and integration*. Jinan: Shandong Education Press.
- [38] [Fa] Paul Langelang (2006). *Lifelong Education: The Development of the Concept, the Encyclopedia of International Education (Volume 5)*. Beijing: Educational Science Press.

- [39] Zhang Taijin (1995). *Higher Education in Britain: History and Status Quo*. Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Publishing organized body.
- [40] Translated by Feng Kley et al. (F · A. Hayek) (2000). *Fatal conceit*. Beijing: China Social Sciences Press.
- [41] Michael Brown (2008). *2010 — Bologna and its influence on the German higher education system of the theory and practice of applied talent training*. Beijing: Higher Education Press.
- [42] Winner Andres (2008). *The theory and practice of cultivating application-oriented talents*. Beijing: Higher Education Press.
- [43] The National Research Center for Education Development (1994). *Trends and Trends in Educational Reform in Developed Countries (episode 5), The Framework of Higher Education in 1991 — White Paper on British Higher Education*. Beijing: The People's Education Press.
- [44] Translated by Wang Chengxu, Xu Hui, et al. (Original work [American] Burton Clark) (2001). *New theory — Multidisciplinary research in higher education*. Hangzhou: Zhejiang Education Press.
- [45] Zou Xiaoping (2009). *Strategic planning theory of local colleges and universities*. Guangzhou: Guangdong Higher Education Press.
- [46] (2021). *Thirty years of exploration and research in higher vocational education*. Beijing: Metallurgical Industry Press.
- [47] By Hu Xiuhai (2021). *Employment vocational education and labor employment*. Beijing, Labor Publishing House
- [48] Chinese Academy of Education Sciences, New Jincheng Research Institute (2021). *China's Vocational Education Quality Annual Report 2020*. Beijing: Higher Education Press.
- [49] Brubeck (2001). *Philosophy of higher education*. Hangzhou: Zhejiang Education Press.
- [50] John Dewey (2001). *Democracy and education*. Beijing: The People's Education Press.
- [51] By Xie Qingsong (2020). *An international comparative study of the seniority framework*. Chongqing: Chongqing University Press.

Foreign language literature:

- [1] UNESDOS. International Standard Classification of Education, 2011 [EB / OL]. [http:// unesdoc.unesdoc.org / images / 0021 / 002191 / 219109e.pdf](http://unesdoc.unesdoc.org/images/0021/002191/219109e.pdf). (2011-0905) [2013-03-25].
- [2] Kathy Reeves Bracco, Richard C. Richardson, Jr., Patrick M. Callan, and Joni E. Finney. Policy Environments and System De-sign: Understanding State Governance Structures. *The Review of Higher Education* 23.1 (1999) 23 -44.
- [3] Douglass C. North, "Institutions", *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 5:1 (Winter 1991): 97-112.
- [4] John Pratt. *The Polytechnic Experiment: 1965-1992* [M]. Buckingham: SRHE and Open University Press. 1997: 321.
- [5] Education for Learning Societies in the 21st century R. statement from the 2nd APCE Education Ministerial Meeting. 7 April 2000: 2.
- [6] Department for Innovation, Universities & Skills. Science and Innovation Investment Framework 2004-2014 [EB/OL]. [http:// www.bis.gov.uk/assets / biscore/ corporate/ migrated D/ publications / 2/2008_economic_impact_report](http://www.bis.gov.uk/assets/biscore/corporate/migrated/D/publications/2/2008_economic_impact_report). Dec. 2008.
- [7] Roger Brown. *Quality Assurance in Higher Education—The UK Experience Since 1992* [M]. RoutledgeFalmer Published, 2004: 115.
- [8] Scott P. *The Meanings of Mass Higher Education* [M]. Buckingham: Open University Press, 1995: 169.
- [9] Peter Wright. *What Should Institutions and Academics do in Response to the Dearing Report?* <http://www.inge.com/docs/wright.htm>.
- [10] National Committee of Inquiry into Higher Education (1997): *Higher Education in The Learning Society [The Dearing Report] Summary Report*.
- [11] Umap. "Overview of dimensions and indicators," [http://u - map.org/U - Map% 20dimensions % 20 and % 20 indicators% 20 overview.pdf](http://u-map.org/U-Map%20dimensions%20and%20indicators%20overview.pdf). 2010-09-13.
- [12] Chris Trott. "Berlin Conference on Typology Transparency in Diversity-Towards a Classification of European Higher Education Institutions," http://www.go8.edu.au/storage/About_go8/european_liaison/Report-Towards_a_Classification_of_European_HE_institutions.pdf. 2010-09-13.
- [13] American Productivity and Quality Center (APQC). *The Corporate University: Measuring the Impact of Learning* [M]. APQC International Benchmarking Clearinghouse, Houston, TX, 2000.
- [14] Prince, C. & Beaver, G *The Rise and Rise of the Corporate University: the emerging corporate learning agenda* [J]. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 2001, 2(3): 17-26.
- [15] Douglass C. North, "Institutions", *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 5:1 (Winter 1991): 97-112.
- [16] Kathy Reeves Bracco, Richard C. Richardson, Jr., Patrick M. Callan, and Joni E. Finney. Policy Environments and System De-sign: Understanding State Governance Structures. *The Review of Higher Education* 23.1 (1999) 23 -44.

Chinese paper:

- [1] Jiang Dayuan (2011). Rational inquiry of the construction of modern vocational education system. *Education research*.2011(11)。
- [2] Li Xiaoming (2012). Industrial transformation and upgrading and the development of higher vocational undergraduate education —— Local application-oriented undergraduate transformation of higher vocational undergraduate education as the choice. *Research on educational development*.2012(3)。
- [3] Xiao Haitao, Xiang Chun (2007).—— Based on the perspective of school system reform. *Research on Higher Engineering Education*.2007(1)。
- [4] Shi Weiping, Xu Guoqing (2003). On the significance and strategy of developing technology undergraduate course in China. *Research on educational development*.2003(12)。
- [5] Fan Mingcheng (2012). Background, problem and prospect of higher vocational education level orientation in China. *Heilongjiang Higher Education Research*, 2010 (5).
- [6] Xiao Fengxiang, Dong Xianhui (2020). Optimization of the hierarchical structure of vocational education in China under the perspective of system theory. *Vocational and technical education*.2020(13)。
- [7] Xu Han (2019). Thinking on building a modern vocational education system with Chinese Characteristics. *Vocational and technical education in China*.2019(12)。
- [8] Liu Zhiyun (2010). Research on the system of mass higher Education in China. *Modern University Education*, 2010 (6).
- [9] Hu Shougen, Yin Gram, Yang Xuhui (2019). Thoughts on the popularization of regional Higher Education and the development orientation of new undergraduate universities. *On Higher education studies in China*.2019(1)。
- [10] Liu Xiaomin (2017). We will build an applied university of science and technology to train and train highly skilled personnel. *Educational Development Research*, 2017 (17).
- [11] Yang Jintu (2020). The type of vocational education at the undergraduate education level in China. *Educational Development Research*, 2020 (1).
- [12] Pan Maoyuan (2018). Establishing an independent system of higher vocational education. *Education research*.2018 (5)。
- [13] Guo Yang (2017). Research on the strategy of developing technology undergraduate course in China. *Vocational and Technical Education (Education edition)*, 2017 (1).
- [14] Lei Shiping, Jiang Qunying (2015). Junior college higher vocational college upgrade undergraduate course "policy mouth" why cannot open. *Journal of Henan Vocational and Technical Normal College (Vocational Education edition)*.2015(1)。
- [15] Xu Hui (2017). Study on the effective way to develop higher vocational education at the undergraduate level. *Chinese adult education*.2017(23)。
- [16] Gu Kunhua (2019). It is a rational choice to develop the higher vocational education undergraduate course actively. *Vocational and technical education*, 2019 (26).
- [17] Yang Jintu (2013). The objectivity of technical undergraduate education. *Vocational Education Forum*, 2013 (1).
- [18] Li Xiaojun, Xia Jianguo (2016). Higher technical education: an internationally recognized type of education. *Vocational education forum*.2016(7)。
- [19] Li Yanxia, Xia Jianguo (2011). Curriculum system reform: technical undergraduate education together around the obstacles. *Vocational education forum*.2011(13)。
- [20] Chen Fei (2017) Reflections on the development of technical undergraduate education. *Research on educational development*.2017(17)。
- [21] Wang Hongcai (2014). How should China develop applied technology universities. *College education management*.2014(6)。
- [22] Jiang Dayuan (2012). Translation order of the federal vocational education law. *Vocational and technical education in China*.2012(10)。
- [23] Dong Liping (2014). Local universities transformation development and construction of applied technology universities. *Education research*.2014(8)。

- [24] Xie Lizhong (2001). The meaning analysis of "modernity" and its related concepts. *Journal of Peking University (Philosophy and Social Sciences edition)*.2001(5)。
- [25] Zhang Jian (2020). On the construction of the modern vocational education system with the integration as the core. *Education and occupation*.2020(17)。
- [26] and shock (2019). On the connotation and characteristics of modern vocational Education. *Higher Education Research in China*, 2019 (10).
- [27] Chen Peng, Pang Xuegang (2013). Cultivate full professional people —— the theoretical ideas about modern vocational education. *Education research*.2013(1)。
- [28] Coat to Hui (2020). Analysis of the training objective and connotation of higher vocational education at the undergraduate level. *Vocational and technical education in China*.2020(27)。
- [29] Uncle Yang (1999). Modern universities and the humanities education. *And Higher Education Studies*.1999(4)。
- [30] Release (1997). On quality education in universities. *Education research*.1997(11)。
- [31] Bao Guoguang (2006). Social needs, the lack of technology, and the birth of machines. The study of the dialectics of nature.2006(1)。
- [32] Nie Wei (2018). Discussion on integrating the new undergraduate colleges into the construction of modern vocational education system —— On the boundary of vocational education. *On Higher education studies in China*.2018(11)。
- [33] Han Yanming (2003). Analysis of the concept, educational concept and university concept. *Education research*.2003(9)。
- [34] Ma Luting (2014). Some thoughts on the construction of Applied Technology University. *Chinese Higher Education*.2014(10)。
- [35] Xiao Weiping (2021). Analysis on the Optimization of Higher Education in China under the View of System Theory. *Modern educational science*.2021(2)。
- [36] Li Xiaojun, Xia Jianguo (2015), the development path of technical undergraduate universities under the vision of building a strong higher education country. *On Higher education studies in China*.2015(4)。
- [37] Liu Jiaomin (2013). We will build an applied university of science and technology to train and train highly skilled personnel. *Research on educational development*.2013(17)。
- [38] Zhou Jiansong (2011). Thinking on the comprehensive construction of the modern vocational education system. *On Higher education studies in China*.2011(7)。
- [39] Meng Fanhua (2011). Lu Xin stressed: to promote the construction of a modern vocational education system. *Vocational and technical education*.2011(15)。
- [40] Zhang Qidifficult, Li Yujing (2011)."12th Five-Year" system —— The Ministry of Education held a symposium on the compilation of national special plans for the construction of modern vocational education system. *Vocational and technical education*.2011(30)。
- [41] Zhao Hongqiang (2018). Classified management and diversified development of higher education. *Jiangsu higher education*.2018(4)。
- [42] Li Hongwei (2019).—— On the path of developing higher vocational undergraduate courses in China. *Vocational education forum*.2019(7)。
- [43] Yin Weimin (2013). The Practice and exploration of the construction of modern vocational education system in Jiangsu province. *Vocational and technical education in China*.2013(36)。
- [44] Song Kehui, Tian Shenghui, etc. (2012). Knowledge, ability, quality structure and training of applied talents. *And Higher Education Studies*.2012(7)。
- [45] Lu Wuxia (2017). The policy orientation and system orientation of higher vocational curriculum construction. *Vocational and technical education*.2017(27)。
- [46] Jiang Dayuan (2009). Cross-border thinking of vocational education legislation —— reflection based on German experience. *Research on educational development*.2009(19)。
- [47] Huang Shaorong (2011). Analysis of the problems of cost sharing compensation in higher vocational education in China. *Reform and strategy*.2011(10)。

- [48] Zhang Changmin, Huang Yiwu, Wang Zulin (2016). Industry-university-research cooperation is an effective way to improve the quality and level of higher education —— Based on a questionnaire survey of 412 universities, some enterprises, research institutes and graduate students. *Proceedings of the 2016 China Industry-University-Research Cooperative Education Summit*.2016。
- [49] Chagid (2017). Investigation and research on the cooperation willingness of enterprises and vocational colleges in Guangzhou. *Vocational and technical education in China* 17 (29)..20
- [50] Su Xin, Hou Pengcheng (2016). The structure diversification and value conflict of higher education evaluation system. *Education research*.20016(10)。
- [51] Sun Cheng, Du Yunying (2014). The development idea of the European University of Applied Technology. *Chinese Higher Education*.2014(12)。
- [52] Tension (2000). Educational function differentiation and government responsibility positioning.research trends.2000(14)。
- [53] Corning (2014) Discussion on the income of higher education investment in the era of knowledge economy. *Education research*.2014(12)。
- [54] Zhai Haixin (2006). The Law of the development of world vocational education —— a historical perspective. *Journal of Hebei Normal University (Education Science Edition)*.2006(3)。
- [55] Mu Guangzong (1998). Economic globalization and Chinese population: historic opportunities and challenges. *The contemporary world and socialism*.1998(3)。
- [56] Xue Rongjiu (1998). The influence and challenge of economic globalization.world economy.1998(4)。
- [57] Jiang Dayuan, Wang Zerong, et al. (2016). Research on the development trend of contemporary world vocational education —— Phenomenon and laws (one) —— The trend of extended development based on horizontal dimension: boundary setting and crossover. *Vocational and technical education in China*.2016(18)。
- [58] The Education Management Information Center of the Ministry of Education (1995). Our Competitive Future: The White Paper on Building a Knowledge Economy. *The World Education Information*.1995(5)。
- [59] Pan Faqin (2004). Future development strategies for UK higher education. *Future and development*.2004(1)。
- [60] Li Chunsheng (2001). Japan has issued the 21st Century Education Freshmen Plan. *The World Education Information*.2001(5)。

Other documents:

- [1] Chai Wei, Gao Yizhe. Wan Li Kunpeng is holding, education spring breeze is growing —— held around the education work conference to introduce the education planning outline overview [N]. *China Education Daily*, 2011-05-30.
- [2] Wang Sujie. Jiangsu "400" transfer students have no school status also on higher vocational [N]. *Chinese Youth*, 2013-12-11.
- [3] Li Jianping. How long is the transition period of local newly built undergraduate universities [N]. *China Youth Daily*, 2014-07-03.
- [4] The transformation of local undergraduate universities (Education Vision · Focus on the transformation of some undergraduate universities (bottom)) [N]. *People's Daily*, 2014-05-08.
- [5] Yuan Guiren.——'s speech at the 2012 National Education Work Conference [N]. *China Education Daily*, 2012-2-21.
- [6] Lu Xin. Speech at the 2012 National Education Work Conference [N]. *China Education Daily*, 2012-2-21.
- [7] The transformation of local undergraduate universities (Education Vision · Focus on the transformation of some undergraduate universities (top)) [N]. *People's Daily*, 2014-05-08.
- [8] Lu Xin: Develop modern vocational education to solve the structural contradiction in employment. *China Development Forum* 2014.
- [9] The Research Group of the Chinese Academy of Education Sciences. European University of Applied Technology [R].2013-12-10.
- [10] University of Applied Technology (College) Alliance, local University Transformation and Development research Center. Research report on the transformation and development practice and policy of local undergraduate institutions [R].2013-11.
- [11] Liu Laiquan. World Overview of Technical and Vocational Education —— report from the UNCO [R].north
Jing: Higher Education Press, 2002:68.

- [12] The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. The World Education Report (1993) [R].1994:144.
- [13] The Center for Enterprise and Education Research, Peking University. Ericsson China University Survey Report and Interview Summary [R]. Enterprise and Education Research Center, Peking University, 2011-05.
- [14] Alliance of Applied Technology Universities, Research Center for Transformation and Development of local universities. Compilation of the transformation and development data of ordinary undergraduate colleges and universities.2014(1).
- [15] International theory on the integrated development strategy of industry and education http://info.huanghuai.edu.cn/gb/zmdforum/lmgylt/21_48_08_59.htm.
- [16] 178 universities issued the Zhumadian Consensus to promote the transformation and development of local universities and build universities of applied technology with Chinese characteristics. China Education News Network, 2014-04-28.
- [17] Introduction to Shenzhou College [EB / OL].(2008-09-08)[2013-3-28] <http://si.cast.cn/Article/ShowInfo.asp?InfoID=3>.
- [18] We have a long way to go to build a " big country of skilled workers. People's Daily Online, 2014-05-26. <http://politics.people.com.cn/n/2014/0526/c1001-25066530.html>.
- [19] University of Applied Technology Alliance.<http://www.auas.org.cn/index.htm>.
- [20] The Bologna process.<http://baike.sogou.com/v63152489.htm>.
- [21] The Education Office of the Embassy of the People's Republic of China in the Federal Republic of Germany. German University Directory 2011 (5).[EB/OL].http://www.de-moe.edu.cn/article_read.php?id=12057-20110525-995.2011-05-25.
- [22] The Bureau of National Statistics.<http://data.stats.gov.cn/workspace/index?m=hgnd>

Author Information

Li Yanyan

Krirk University, Bangkok, Thailand

Zhang Jiayong

Krirk University:No.3 Soi Ramintra 1, Ramintra Road, Anusawaree, BangKhen, Bangkok 10220, Thailand.